

Analyzing the kinetic behavior of hydrides applying the Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) method

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Abstract

Hydrogen is considered the most promising energy vector for an energy matrix based on renewable energy sources. There are several bottlenecks for the broad utilization of hydrogen; among them, its storage poses a challenge. Hydrogen storage in solid materials can provide a more compact, efficient, and safer alternative than the conventional physical storage methods in gaseous or liquid state [1].

These hydrogen storage systems comprise a vessel containing a hydride-forming material whose hydrogenation and dehydrogenation kinetic behaviors require appropriate characterization and modeling to gain a deeper understanding of the reaction mechanism [2]. This work explores a novel application of the Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) method to determine the rate-limiting step (RLS) of an AB₂ hydride-forming alloy (Ti_{0.9}Zr_{0.1})_{1.25}Cr_{0.85}Mn_{1.1}Mo_{0.05} to which 10 wt.% of expanded natural graphite (ENG) was added [3]. Results obtained from measurements in Sieverts apparatus in broad ranges of temperature and hydrogen pressures (from -25 °C to about 40 °C and from 1 bar to about 160 bar) have been analyzed through this method to evaluate the JMAK equation (Johnson-Mehl-Avrami-Kolmogorow) [4]. To determine their most probable values, the MCMC approach focuses on the statistical distribution of the exponential factor n, describing the RLS, and the kinetic rate constant k for each kinetic curve. Considering the obtained n, the RLS mechanisms for the hydrogenation and dehydrogenation processes show a clear dependence on the T and P conditions.

On the one hand, for the hydrogenation process, the RLS changes from a mixed mechanism (interphase movement and diffusion control, n= 0.7-0.8) to a pure interphase movement control mechanism as the temperature and pressure increase (n= 1.0-1.24). On the other hand, for the dehydrogenation process, the RLS is mainly the interphase movement at low temperatures and pressures (n= 1.0-1.25) and changes to a mixed mechanism as the temperature and pressure increase (n= 0.8-0.9). However, the interphase movement dominates the mixed mechanism in the T and P range. This analysis provides novel insights into the determination of the RLS, something impossible to reach with the application of the traditional gas-solid model determination methods (linearization of the gas-solid equations and reduced time method [4]).

References

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